

TRIBHUVAN UNIVERSITY
Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

SUBVERSION OF PATRIARCHY IN PAUDEL'S *APABITRA RAGAT [UNHOLY
BLOOD]*

A Thesis

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By

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LETTER OF RECOMMENDATION

This thesis entitled “Subversion of Patriarchy in Paudel’s *Apabitra Ragat [Unholy Blood]*” has been prepared by Sushma Gurung under my supervision. I assert that this thesis has maintained the necessary scope and intensity of its level. The researcher has worked well and she has presented the findings systematically. Thus, I hereby recommend it for acceptance and examination.

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EVALUATION AND APPROVAL

It is approved that the thesis entitled “Subversion of Patriarchy in Paudel’s *Apabitra Ragat [Unholy Blood]*” prepared by Sushma Gurung has been submitted to the Department of English, Mahendra Multiple Campus, Dharan, Sunsari. It has been accepted and evaluated by the following thesis evaluation committee.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis is my original work, and it contains no materials previously published in my name. I have not used its materials for the award of any kind or any other degree. The authors and resources of information that are used to support my argument have been duly acknowledged.

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this dissertation is to identify the subversion of patriarchy, to analyze why the author has subverted it, and how it is subverted in the text, *Apabitra Ragat*. The research has especially highlighted the conservative patriarchal practice of menstruation and its impact on girls and women and also foregrounds the problems of marginalized women. Radical feminism has been used as a tool for the analysis that calls for restructuring the society where the male's superiority is eliminated by challenging patriarchal values and institutions. It struggles against the sexual objectification of women, traditional gender roles and capitalism, and thus demands an alternative to patriarchal structure in which women get justice. Patriarchal society has brainwashed women through the standardized concepts such as family, beauty, academy, peace, gender roles and marriage. It is precisely through these concepts that males have continued their domination over women. Thus, radical feminists seek to eliminate the gender, break the hierarchy of sexes and thus abolish the oedipal family relation to create a society without hierarchy

The findings from this research are that the Menstruations is inhumane patriarchal society based on race, gender, ability, socio economic status, sexual orientation, age, religion and so on. This isolates and prohibits menstruating girls and women staying in the house with family members, going to the temple, cooking food and so on. Moreover, it deprives them from having dairy products and other nutritious foods like meat. They are regarded impure and polluted. They have to hide in the shed during their menstruation. These menstrual stigmas, taboos and these rules are constructed by men which can be deconstructed by men. The paudel along with the

other characters in the novel work to dismantle the patriarchy. The speakers express their anger against gender discrimination and their call for a just society. They are the agent of change. The study concludes that self-awakening, education, political revolutions have caused the subversive effort. It also shows that the continuous and collective effort is necessary to destroy both physical and mental menstruation taboos and stigma.

This research helps the readers to understand how patriarchy can be subverted through autobiography. Since radical feminism has been used for analysis, it will contribute to the better understanding of radical feminism to the researchers who want to apply it in their researches. It will be useful to understand the power relationship between the sexes in a patriarchal society like Nepal.

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LIST OF TRANSLITERATION OF DEVANAGARI ALPHABETS

English Alphabets	Devnagari
a	अ
ā	आ
I	इ
ī	ई
u	उ
ū	ऊ
ṛ	ऋ
e	ए
ai	ऐ
o	ओ
au	औ
ka	क
kha	ख
ga	ग

gha	घ
ca	च
cha	छ
ja	ज
jha	झ
ṭa	ट
ṭha	ठ
ḍa	ड
ṇa	ण
ta	त
tha	थ
na	न
pa	प
pha	फ
ba	ब
bha	भ
ma	म

ya	य
ra	र
la	ल
va (pronounced as /b/)	व
wa (pronounced as /w/)	व
śa	श
sa	स
ha	ह

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Radha Paudel is a renowned Nepali writer, feminist, nurse and human rights activist. She is widely recognized for her impactful writings, which focus on social issues, women's rights, and gender equality in Nepal. She has dedicated her life to advocating for women's rights, working to end gender-based violence and discrimination, and empowering women through education and economic opportunities. Paudel's writing exhibits a strong sense of empathy and compassion. She demonstrates the deep understanding of the challenges faced by marginalized groups, particularly women, and gives voice to their struggle. She has worked with various non-governmental organizations and community groups in Nepal, providing support and assistance to women who have experienced violence, abuse, and exploitation.

In addition to her advocacy work, she has written several books including *Khalaṅgāmā hamalā*, *Dignified Mensuration*, *The Journey of the Light of the Lamp from Lamjung to London*, *Apabitra Ragat*. In 2014, Paudel received the Madan Puraskar for her book '*Khalanga ma Hamala*' which was later translated into English and titled, '*Jumla: A Nurse's Story*'. *Khalaṅgāmā hamalā* is about Paudel's experience in Jumla, primarily sharing about the attack on Jumla's headquarters by then-rebel Maoists on November 14, 2002.

Her recent creation is an autobiography, *Apabitra Ragat* (2018). It reflects about the author's struggle to dignified menstruation. The author promotes feminist voices and subverts patriarchy by resisting male values of the society. It deals about

the superstitious belief of menstrual taboos and stigmas in Nepal. *Apabitra Ragat* encapsulates the menstrual taboos and stigmas associated with menstruation in Nepal that are deeply rooted in traditional beliefs and social norms. The autobiography is divided into twenty-eight chapters, each of which narrates a story of different menstrual taboos, stigma, and patriarchy in accordance with the person and place. In the book, author has combined several narratives, frequently relying on her personal life as well as the lives of those she has met through her activism.

The word “patriarchy” literally means the rule of the father or the ‘patriarch’ and originally it was used to describe a specific type of male dominated family – the large household of the patriarch which included women, junior men, children, slaves and domestic servants all under the dominant rule of the male. Now it is used more generally to refer to male domination, to the power relationships by which men dominate women and to characterize a system whereby women are kept subordinate in a number of way (Bhasin 2). In *Apabitra Ragat*, the author narrates: “*Pandhrau dinakō bihānai nuhaudai garēkī, cōkhēkī didi, āmā saṅgai pachyaurālē anuhāra chōpēra piḍimā jhulkina. Bālē bhitrabāṭa niskēra achētā ra sānō rātō kapaḍākō ṭukrā di'ē pachi didi cōkhinu bhayō. Ani bhitra pasnu bhayō*” ‘In the morning of fifteen days, elder sister became pure by taking a bath. She covered her face with scarf along with mother. Father came out and gave her *achētā* and a piece of red clothes. She became pure and was given permission to enter inside the house’. (Paudel; my trans; 29). It is an example of patriarchy which is a system of social structures and practices in which men dominate, oppress and exploit women.

Menstrual practices and beliefs are often constructed from gender, religion and culture. Instead of being accepted as a natural biological process signifying a girl's entry into adulthood, for many women and girls, menstruation is associated with restrictions, shame and superstitious beliefs of patriarchy society in Nepal.

Menstruation, biologically and culturally, has often been regarded as the moment of transition in a young girl's life from girlhood to womanhood (Mamo and Fosket 930).

In Nepali society, we have many such values which have been imposed on women and girls such that they are forced to live in cowsheds and refrain from touching others, eating together or entering many communal spaces. But because I believe in science and nature, I am doing everything during my period as I do during other times, such as going to temples, cooking in the kitchen and touching my father (Paudel;par.9).

Chhaupadi is a period taboo practiced among some Hindu communities in Nepal and India, in which menstruating women and girls are required to live outside of their home, often in a shack or hut. In more extreme cases, they are barred from interacting with anyone in the community, banned from attending religious ceremonies, prohibited from eating certain foods, and forced to wear special clothes or eat with certain utensils during their period. *Chhaupadi* comes from the belief that menstruating women are unclean and that they bring bad luck to a community. The isolation that women and girls experience can have negative psychological effects and fatal consequences (Kirkegaard;par.22). In *Apabitra Ragat* chapter nine, author narrates:

“Chitwan Gauriganj, Jahā mērō ghara cha, tyahā pani chhaupadi rahēcha.

Tara chhaupadi na bhanēra para sarēkō, bāhira sarēkō, panchi'ēkō, nachunē bha'ēkō, ṭikā lagā'ēkō, dē'utā risā'ēkō, panditanī bha'ēkō bhanidō rahēcha.

Mērō gharamā pahilō paṭaka Ēkkā'isa dina, dōsrō paṭaka pandhra dina, tēsrō

paṭaka sāta dina vā Ēkkā'isa, pandhra, sāta dina garēra basēpachi gharamā

nai bārē hunē tara paścima nēpālamā bhanē mahinai pichē gōṭhamā basēra

sadhai bārnu pardō rahēcha. Gōṭhamā basē pani ghara bhitra basē pani

chuṭā'unē ra bārñē kurā mukhya rahēcha. Yō paścima nēpāla ra bākī

nēpālakō ēkai rahēcha” ‘Chitwan, Gauriganj is a place where my house is

located, there is also chhaupadi. But, the name given to chhaupadi are

different such as para sarēkō, bāhira sarēkō, panchi'ēkō, nachunē bha'ēkō, ṭikā

lagā'ēkō, dē'utā risā'ēkō, panditanī bha'ēkō In my house, for the first time we

need to stay for twenty one days, second time fifteen days and third time we

need to stay for seven days. After that we can stay in home following the

precaution but in western Nepal, it is necessary to sit in a cowshed every

month. Whether we stay in house or cowshed, the main thing is restriction. It

is same as the east and the rest of Nepal’ (Paudel; my trans; 66)

This is an example of *chhaupadi* which is menstrual taboo and stigma practiced by women in almost every part of Nepal.

Sewa Bhattarai, a journalist writes in Nepali Times “after a career as nurse and writer, Paudel is now a full-time activist trying to address practices like menstruation restriction on women, Paudel is back with a second book *Apavitra Ragat* (Unholy

Blood), and like her previous book, this book also deals with blood-letting. This book is searing in its honesty, and practical difficulties Nepali women face during adolescence: not finding enough rags to soak up the blood, always worrying if the blood is leaking through clothes. The book is graphic, and not for faint-hearted reader as it describes the monthly reality for many Nepali women. She further commented on the language of the book, “The language in the book is regional and therefore adds value to the whole story.”

Speaking about the book in social media, Sudha Gurung said, “The book discusses very delicate aspects of a girl’s life.” She added, “It’s a shame that our society degrades such an indispensable and essential biological process in a woman's life. Fortunately, I have had the opportunity to speak openly on such issues. But when I read about menstruation being stigmatized, it hurts.” She says that the book is worth reading and she is happy to have the opportunity to talk to the author about such issues and praises the author.

Moin Uddin reviews in the social media “This book is spreading awareness to remove the menstrual shame and promote the dignified menstruation by removing the menstrual taboo and stigma”. The story began with the Paudel’s own childhood, and she writes about how her mother and sisters were made to stay away from kitchen and temples during menstruation. Paudel has expressed the reality of menstrual taboo and stigma faced by the many Nepali women in different places in her book.

Dr. Suresh Gautam, Head of Department of Development Education of Kathmandu University School of Education speaks about the autobiography in the

book talk saying “Once I started reading the book, I thought myself that I was born from unholy blood” . That was a kind of impression I have gone through, so then I started asking question to myself am I a holy or unholy? Because our society interprets that menstrual blood is unholy. He also adds, the text in the book has made him to think and reflect on the menstruation issues how we practice in the home. This book is important to everyone how we respect and celebrate the natural process of menstrual cycle. He foregrounds the bitter experience experienced by many women in Nepal.

Though the reviews mentioned above comment about Paudel’s autobiography as the advocacy for the menstrual taboo and stigma of Nepali women and marginalized groups, none of them have made a detailed study of her autobiography *Apavitra Ragat* to trace the subversion of patriarchy in them. They have not discussed in detail about the suffering of women and patriarchy. There is a need of evaluating the patriarchal values which none of the critics have explored. So, this memoirs deserves a further study from the perspective of radical feminism.

Patriarchal society in Nepal prioritizes males over females and belittles women as an inferior gender. Numerous women in Nepal silently endure social mistreatment as a result. Paudel subverts those norms and values that discriminate women. The author has spoken out against stereotypes that justify giving women a lower place in patriarchal societies in several of her writings. My curiosity in researching the author's memoir from a feminist perspective was inspired by the way she subverts such patriarchal conventions and beliefs. Therefore, this research has attempt to find the answer to the following questions:

1. What patriarchal ideologies are depicted in the Autobiography?
2. Why does the narrator subvert the patriarchal ideologies in the Autobiography?
3. How does the narrator subvert the patriarchy in the Autobiography?

Regarding the existence and origin of patriarchy, traditionalists do believe that men are born to dominate and women to be subordinated. Women participate in their own marginalization because they do not see how these values contribute to it.

Women's minds have been so thoroughly ingrained with these values that they regard them as the law of nature. This has led to the sexual dominance and physical, sexual, and psychological exploitation of women. Thus, this research has the following objectives:

1. To identify patriarchal ideologies presented in the autobiography.
2. To explain the reasons why the narrator subverts patriarchal ideologies in the Autobiography.
3. To analyze the way how the narrator subverts the patriarchy in the Autobiography.

This research uses qualitative approach based on study of an autobiography *Apavitra Ragat* as the primary source. Articles, interviews, reviews and comments on autobiography are used as secondary sources. This study makes use of feminist criticism because the autobiography subverts patriarchy in a strong way. Feminist criticism defines a literary theory showing how women were portrayed as less valuable than men in literature throughout history. It also explores how women

writers were taken less seriously than male authors from a historical perspective (Garcia;par.1). Feminist literary criticism looks at literature assuming its production from a male-dominated perspective. It re-examines canonical works to show how gender stereotypes are involved in their functioning. It examines works by women for a possible alternative voice (Spivak 279). According to Lois Tyson, Feminist critical theory examines the oppression of women in literature, how the literature “reinforces or undermines the economic, political, social, and psychological oppression of women” (83). Tyson argues that society is so immersed in patriarchy that we’re programmed “not to see the ways in which women are oppressed by traditional gender roles” (86). Similarly, the author believes that patriarchy is the major obstruction to women's achievement. Therefore, Paudel's *Apabitra Ragat* deserves the study from the perspective of feminist criticism.

The main idea of radical feminism is to understand that gender is not just a product of individual attitudes or behaviors, but rather a systemic and institutionalized form of oppression that pervades all aspects of society. Science journalist and broadcaster Angela Saini begins her stirring interrogation of patriarchy by arguing that it is neither constant, inevitable nor unshakeable. “By thinking about gendered inequality as rooted in something unalterable within us, we fail to see it for what it is,” she writes, “something more fragile that has had to be constantly remade and reasserted” (par.1). Similarly, Lolerie Yang notes, women’s oppression has social, economic, political and psychological aspects and is tied directly to the traditional system of male dominance as the head of the family (par.3). The arguments are sufficient for showing that feminism's main concerns are the exploitation of women

and gender inequality. Feminism thus evolved as a movement that supported women's rights and gender equality in a patriarchal society that had long exploited women.

This research uses radical feminism for the analysis since the author subverts the supremacy of men and demands a critical reevaluation of patriarchal beliefs. Radical feminism sees women as a collective group that has been and is still being oppressed by men. Its intent is focused on being women-centered, with women's experiences and interests being at the forefront of the theory and practice. It is argued by some to be the only theory by and for women (Klein 10). The author of this autobiography also advocates for the elimination of such practices. Radical feminists place particular emphasis on the theme of the body, and on the reappropriation of the body by women, as well as on the freedom of choice. They demand sexual and reproductive freedom. Radical feminism has shown that the oppression of women is a social construct and even a real social system, based on patriarchal culture, control over women bodies and violence (Cottais 11).

The study, primarily takes insight from Kate Millet, Gayle Rubin, Sulamith Firestone, Susan Brownmiller and Mary Daly. Daly claimed that because patriarchy had constructed the positive feminine qualities of nurturance, compassion, and gentleness as well as the negative feminine qualities of pettiness, jealousy, and vanity, women should reject the supposedly good aspects of femininity as well as the obviously bad ones. All feminine characteristics are "man-made constructs" shaped for the purposes of trapping women deep in the prison of patriarchy (59). According to the radical feminists (Brownmiller 1976, Firestone 1974), patriarchy preceded private property. They believe that the original and basic contradiction is between the

sexes and not between economic classes. Similarly, Gayle Rubin saw the sex/gender system as a “set of arrangements by which a society transforms biological sexuality into products of human activity” (159). Paudel’s autobiography is also related to this split because she portrays that our society is a patriarchy society where menstruation is considered as taboo and that women are compelled to accept it. It covers the psychology of women and children, and such practices highlight the difficulties that women face.

In Kate Millet’s strong attempts to counter male dominance, *Sexual Politics*, she analyzes many social patterns and institutions that serve as covert ways of controlling power. She claimed male control of the public and private worlds maintains patriarchy, male control must be eliminated if women are to be liberated. But this is no easy task. To eliminate male control, men and women must eliminate gender— specifically, sexual status, role, and temperament—as it has been constructed under patriarchy (54). Therefore, Millet’s arguments are also appropriate to Paudel’s autobiography because it demonstrates a strong awareness of the difficulties faced by Nepali women, and speaks out in support of their efforts to overthrow the patriarchy.

Consequently, this research goes around the premise: Radha Paudel, in her autobiography *Apabitra Ragat*, presents how Nepali women are oppressed by patriarchy society. The author of the book describes her dreadful encounters with menstrual stigma and taboos in various Nepalese geographical areas. Thus, the research limits to the study on the subversion of patriarchy as presented in the Autobiography *Apabitra Ragat*.

Numerous studies have been conducted on the issues women in patriarchal societies face. However, my research will enable readers to comprehend how patriarchy can be overthrown. Readers who want to use feminist theory in their research will find it useful. It will also be helpful to those who want to conduct research on this autobiography from multiple perspectives. The findings of this study will also enable readers to understand how patriarchy is the fundamental cause of women's oppression. In addition, this study will help readers realize the importance of menstruation and the importance of refuting stigma. Ultimately, this study will inspire female readers in particular to speak out against such patriarchy and menstrual taboos and stigmas practices.

CHAPTER 2

DEFYING THE PATRIARCHY: A TEXTUAL ANALYSIS

Patriarchy has been a dominant force in many societies around the world for centuries. In patriarchal societies, menstruation has been viewed as a symbol of women's inherent difference and perceived as a source of impurity or weakness. Menstruation has historically been treated as something that should be kept private and avoided in public, which has served to reinforce the idea that women's bodies and bodily functions are unclean or taboo. In the regard, Erika M. Thomas explains in her study of menstruation “taboos in both Western and non-Western cultures that in ancient times, taboos were created around elements such as blood pollution produced by the female body” (67). Patriarchal societal norms and values are significantly regulating menstrual practices. In a patriarchal society, women are guided by the “stand of male’s ideology”. Men generally have more freedom and rights than women today as well. As a result, some modern authors criticize this dominance. Radha Paudel’s autobiography *Apabitra Ragat* is about the subverting of such patriarchy in the society faced by Nepali women.

According to Kate Millet, “Western social arrangements and institutions as covert ways of manipulating power so as to establish and perpetuate the domination of men and the subordination of women” (Abrams 124). Such brutality of patriarchy is clear from the news that being broadcasted every day. *The Online Khabar* reports that “the 29-year-old man had raped an 8-year-old girl in neighborhood in Dang District. Women are also beaten to death in dowry issue. Sajira Shrestha writes that “Dowry Still Killing Dreams in Nepal’s Terai; the wife was beaten mercilessly by her

husband who is doctor serving at reputed hospital in the Kathmandu (Shrestha;par.2)". *The Guardian* reports that "A 16-year-old girl from Nepal has died as a result of the illegal practice of *chhaupadi*, where menstruating women are forced to stay in huts outside their homes (Adhikari;par.1)". Majority of violence that are heard or seen happens to be on women. A protest against such inhumanity is necessary in this situation. The author protest such violence of patriarchy in the Nepali society which needs a critical interpretation. Thus, in the coming sections, I analyze the autobiography *Apabitra Ragat* that subverts patriarchy.

2.1. Perception of Menstruation

In *Apabitra Ragat*, Radha Paudel portrays about her horrifying experiences with menstruation stigma and taboos across multiple geographical areas of Nepal. She asserts that perception of mensuration are influenced by historical, cultural, social, and religious aspects which plays the crucial role to oppress the females. There are levels of severity of menstrual restriction that depend on several intersecting factors such as the education levels of males and females in the household, location, religious background and caste/ethnic background (Subedi 3). The following narration of author express the same idea:

Tyahī pisāba phērna jādā uhālē thōrai rātō raṅga dēkhnu bha'ēcha. Dara bhandā pani uhālā'ī sankā lagyō. Mahināvārī bha'ēkō hō ki haina bhannē ki na bhannē. Jukālē ṭōkyō ki bhannu bhanē pani hi'udakō mahinā kasarī pō jukā laglāna ra? Āmālā'ī bhannu ki na bhannu? Ahilē bhanē ra arkō paṭaka vā arkō mahinā bha'ēna bhanē āmālē ra gā'um̃lēlē kē sōclāna? Mērō kurā

*kāṭa chan mērō caritramāthi saṅkā garchana. Nabhanu pachī dhērai ragata
bha'ē kē garnē? Bā, bhā'ī vā gharamā kēhi narāmrō bhāihālē kasarī samālnē,
mērō kāraṅalē narāmrō bhayō bhannē thāhā pā'ē kē garnē, chaṭapaṭī bhayō.
Āturī lagyō.*

While going to pee, she saw a little red color. She felt doubt rather than fear. Whether to tell or not about having mensuration. Even if I tell that I was bite off by a leech, how can it be possible to get leech in winter? Should I tell the mother or not? If I tell now and if it does not happen next time or next month, what will the mother and the villagers think? They will gossip about me and doubt my character. If I didn't tell but what to do if there will be more blood? If something bad happened to my father, brother, or home, how to deal with the situation, what to do if they find everything bad happening is due to me. I felt stressed and eager. (Paudel; my trans; 30-31)

These lines indicate the women's oppression in a patriarchy society. One of the most widespread misconceptions about menstruation in Nepal is that women who are going through it are impure and shouldn't be touched. This ideology has resulted in discrimination and isolation, with women being excluded from their communities during their menstrual cycles and forced to live separately (Lamsal;par.7).

Instead of being accepted as a natural biological process signifying a girl's entry into adulthood, for many women and girls, menstruation is associated with restrictions, shame and superstitious beliefs (Mukherjee 2). Such perception of menstruation scared and traumatized author to commit suicide because she did not

want to live as a girl. The author narrates; “*Malāṭi ji'unu nai bēkāra jastō lāgna thālyō. Mahināvārī nai samājamā mahilā māthi hunē sampūrṇa vibhēdakō mūla curō hō bhannē lagyō.*” ‘I started to feel that living is useless. Menstruation is the root of all discrimination against women in the society.’ (Paudel; my trans; 32). She claims that during her childhood, she witnessed her elder sisters being mistreated by neighbors and other villages when they stayed in the cowshed during their periods. Despite she didn’t end her life, the author never gave up dreaming of becoming a man in a patriarchal society where the odds were always against women.

The author further claims that women are unaware of how miserable their lives are in a patriarchal society. Lack of adequate perception towards menstruation may make girls vulnerable to mental, emotional, and physical problems, especially during their menstruating days (Belayneh 1). With fear and countless questions in her mind, Paudel asks:

Kina kēṭharu vā mahilāharu mahināvārī hunchan?

Yadi mahināvārī bha'ēna bhanē kē huncha hōlā?

Mahināvārī bārnuparnē cāhiṃ kina hōlā?

Yadi mahināvārī bārēna bhanē kē huncha hōlā?

Yasarī bārdā sakasa bha'ēkō kurā kina, kasailē pani nabhanēkō hōlā?

Yō sakasabāṭa kasarī mukti pā'incha hōlā?

Why do girls or women have periods?

What will happen if menstruation doesn't occur?

Why is it necessary to practice menstruation?

What will happen if menstruation is not practiced?

Why did no one speak about such miserable practice?

How can you get rid of this miserable practice? (Paudel; my trans; 31)

These questions indicate that women feel pressured to adhere to patriarchal perceptions of menstruation. They feel embarrassed of their natural bodily function and are fearful of being blamed for bringing bad fortune if they do not strictly follow the menstrual restrictions imposed on them by society (Robinson 193). According to Kate Millett, to eliminate male control, men and women must eliminate gender “specifically, sexual status, role, and temperament” as it has been constructed under patriarchy. Therefore, the author identifies patriarchal society as responsible for the oppression of women.

The manner in which a girl perceives about menstruation and its associated changes may have an impact on her response to the event of menarche (Lawan 2). Paudel's understanding about menstruation started the day she saw menstrual blood on her mother's leg. She was concerned as no information or education was given to her about it. Later when her menstrual cycle started, she realized that she was seen differently by her mother and other family members. The onset of the first menstrual period is a qualitative event of major significance changes in a woman's life, denoting

the achievement of major functional states in social-, occupational-, and health-related aspects (Lee 28). The lines below depict the author's perceptions and sufferings:

*Mailē ta pisāba phērna pardaina, carpī, pyāḍa, pānī, sābunabārē sōcnu
pardaina bhanēra dinabhara pānī khā'ēna. Pyāḍa pani dinabhara phērina.
Kahilē ta tēhī pyāḍa lagā'ēra du'ī tīna dina pani basē. Kahilē kāgaja lagā'ē.
Kahilē mailō ṭālō lagā'ē. Jē pā'ēm̃ tyahi lagā'ē. Dhēraijasō mirgaulā rōga ra
yaunānga rōga lāgnē kāraṇa pani yēhī mahinābārī rahēcha. Dhilai bha'ē pani
svasthākarmīkō svara sunna pā'ē. Samjhēra pani āṅga nai siriṅga bhayō.*

I didn't drink water all day so that I don't have to think about pee, wipes, pads and soap. Even didn't changed the pads in the whole day. Sometime stayed using same pads for two or three days. Sometimes used paper. Sometimes wore dirty clothes. Wore what I get. Mostly the kidney diseases and genital diseases are caused by menstruation. Even though late I could hear the voice of the health worker. Even remembering it, my body was squirming. (Paudel; my trans; 184)

Paudel shares her findings wherein even educated Nepali women who use pads or cups do not have dignified menstruation. "It is not just lack of knowledge but the continuing myths and superstitions around menstruation in this 21st Century that come as a shocker," exclaims Paudel. In autobiography, she reveals that girls during menstruation are still subject to restrictions like not visiting temples or entering the kitchen. "This unnecessary isolation and seclusion puts the spotlight on a girl during her period much to her dismay and embarrassment". Women having better knowledge

and perception regarding menstruation are more likely to have safe menstrual hygiene practice (Czerwinski 125). The author believes, talking openly about menstruation is the only way to transform the voices and denounces patriarchy.

2.2. Menstrual Taboos and Stigmas

In Paudel's autobiography, she represents menstrual taboos and stigma manifest in various ways across different cultures and societies, often leading to discrimination, shame, and a lack of access to proper menstrual hygiene resources and education. She asserts that menstrual taboo and stigma plays a crucial role in creation of patriarchy, and condemns for oppressing the females. The following lines express the same idea:

Pakkai puruṣalē hunu parcha. Kāṃḍālē kōpdā sahana nasaknē puruṣa. Alikati ragata āyō bhanē haṃ haṃ.. Bhandai jvarō nikālnē puruṣa. Mahilālā'ī ta yatikā ragata ā'uṃdā pani nadukhnē. Narunē. Kēhī nahunē bha'ēra risa, ḍ'āha, ḍaralē hōlā niyama pani yastō banā'ēkō. Āphnai surakṣā hōs bhanēra. Marī'ēlā ki, birāmī pari'ēlā ki bhannē ḍaralē bhanēkō hunuparcha- āyu ghaṭcha bhanēra. Birāmī parchana bhanēra. Ani lahai lahaimā ḍarā'ē mahilā pani. Śrīmānakō'āyu ghaṭlā bhanēra ākhira bāhiraphēra ga'ēra kamā'una ta puruṣalā'ī nai parcha. Parivāra pālna pani sajilō ta kahāṃ cha ra? Ēkadina haina, ēka haptā vā mahinā pani hō'ina. Sadhaim̃ sadhaim̃ pō dhānnu parcha ta parivāra. Sāyada samājalē yahī bhancha.

Of course, men should be. A man who cannot bear to be pricked by thorns. If there is a little blood, the man who takes the fever by saying *han han ...* A

woman does not feel pain even when bleeding so much. Never cry. There is nothing happening to them that's why their anger, jealousy, and fear might have made the rules like this. For their own safety. They are fear of dying or getting sick must have meant that the life expectancy will decrease. To not get sick. And the woman was also scared. After all, it is up to the man to go out and earn because the life of his husband will decrease. Where is it easy to raise a family? Not a day, not even a week or a month. You have to always take care of your family. Maybe this is what society says. (Paudel; my trans; 12)

In these lines, Paudel states that menstrual taboos are those customs often found in the tribal society that publicly restrict the behavior of menstruation and apply throughout most of a woman's life. The menstrual taboos and stigmas are found profoundly in the community. Common period taboos include the idea that women are impure, dirty, or sinful while they're menstruating. Some women are discouraged from touching or washing their genitals during their periods to eliminate the possibility that they might contaminate the water of a communal bathing area (Kirkegaard; par. 9). Such practice hinders women to compete along with men, and make their own identity.

Among many religious myths, in many rural parts of Nepal, people practice *Chaupadi Pratha*, It is an ancient tradition practiced in some rural parts of Nepal. It involves banishing people, often young girls, to mud huts or sheds for the duration of their menstruation, or even longer. The tradition, associated with Hinduism, controls what a woman can eat, where she sleeps and who she can interact with during her monthly cycle. Many adherents believe that disobeying the rules invites misfortune

and death (Budhathoki;par. 7). Paudel attacks such traditions which hinder women's progress.

Despite being illegal, *chhaupadi*, the practice of exiling menstruating women and girls from their home – often to a cow shed – is still practiced in some areas of Western Nepal. *Chhaupadi* is an extreme example of the stigmas and restrictions around menstruation that exist not only in Nepal, but also globally (Sara;par. 2). The extract given below reveal this:

Vāstabamā chā'upaḍī sansārabhara cha, jahām̐ jahām̐ nēpālī chan. Bārnē tarikā ra mātrā kēhī tala-māthi, dhērai-thōrai hōlā. Tara yasaḱō antaravastu vā sidānta'ēkai hō. Chā'upaḍī bhandā paścima nēpālālā'ī thapa vibhēda hunē manasāyalē yasalā'ī mahināvārī bārnē calana, bhannu baḍhī sāndarbhika huncha.

Actually *Chhaupadi* is all over the world, wherever live Nepalese. The method of practicing menstruation may be a little lower-higher, a lot-less. But its essence or principle is the same. It is more relevant to call it a custom of menstruation with the intention of distinguishing West Nepal more than *Chhaupadi*. (Paudel; my trans; 189)

In these lines, she denounces patriarchy society for creating social barriers and rules on women to do or not to do social and religious activities at home and outside during menstruation. She tells that not only in the western Nepal, *Chhaupadi* is practiced in different ways all over Nepal. As stated by Gayle Rubin, in the process of accomplishing this task, patriarchal society convinced itself that its cultural

constructions are somehow natural and therefore that people's normality depends on their ability to display whatever gender identities and behaviors are culturally linked with their biological sex. The task for feminists is therefore to contest the normativity of "naturalness" and to proclaim the fluidity of all categories of gender (54).

Paudel says "Menstrual isolation is a human right violation, it isolates women by barring them from kitchens, water sources, temples, schools, and homes". Religious myths justify women subjugation to men. They teach women to be submissive, quiet, tolerant, and loyal to men. According to Valerie Julliard et al., "women and girls are excluded from key community activities every month. This may affect their education; their ability to contribute productively; their income and their representation and leadership in decision making in the home and community". Such practice hinders women to compete along with men, and make their own identity. Paudel protest such traditions which hinder women's progress. Thus, she claims that the moral of religious myth is obstructing women to maintain their identity independent.

Attack on the patriarchy society can be read in the autobiography. "*Mailē asaṅkhyā'āmā-bālā'ī aparādhī ra pāpī dēkhēm, jasalē mahināvārīkō nāmamā chōrīharulā'ī du: Kha mātra di'ēnan, Vibhēda mātra garēnan arulā'ī pani hēlā garna vibhēda garna utprērita garē.*" 'I have seen many parents who are criminals and sinners, who not only hurt their daughters in the name of menstruation, but also discriminated against them and encouraged others to discriminate.' (Paudel; my trans; 51). Here, she tells that parents, who should be the protectors and nurturers of their children, engage in criminal and sinful behavior. It is even more disturbing when

these actions are directed toward their daughters under the guise of menstruation. This discrimination not only hurts these young girls physically and emotionally but also perpetuates a cycle of inequality and injustice. She tells that she will not allow anybody to consider her an object created by them, and rule over her ruthlessly.

Women are ignorant of the fact that the instructions provided by the religions they follow are responsible for their suppression. In *Apabitra Ragat*, she raises women's awareness about their oppression and encourages them to protest against oppressive religious mythology:

*Chōrīlā'ī binā praśna bāṁcna sikā'uṁcha samājalē. Bādhyā pārcha
samudāyalē. Yahī samājamā ē'uṭai āmālē janmā'ēkō chōrālē pani pāṁca-
cha barṣakō huṁdā mahināvārībārē thāhā mātra pā'uṁdaina, usalē ma mērī didi
vā āmābhandā ṭhulō huṁ bhannē, cōkhō huṁ bhannē, śaktiśālī huṁ bhannē
manōbhāva pani hurkā'uṁcha. Kinabhanē usalē mahināvārī hunu
pardaina. Usalē jē pani khāna pā'uṁcha. Kasailē usalā'ī sōdhaina.*

The society teaches the daughter to live without any question. The society forced. In this society, a son born by the same mother does not only learn about menstruation when he is five or six years old, he also grows up thinking that I am bigger than my sister or mother, that I am pure, that I am powerful. Because he doesn't have to menstruate. He can eat anything. No one asks him.

(Paudel; my trans; 150)

The author affirms that patriarchy wrote the norms and values in the religious books, and taught women to follow them since their childhood. The religious mythology has

taught women to tolerate all the sufferings without any objections, remain passive and submissive. Such religious myths and the idea of God are questioned by Mary Daly. Daly comments “If God is male, then the male is God”. All those characters attributed to God, like strength, wisdom, immutability, dependability, and righteousness, are similar to values stereotypically attributed to men, whereas weakness, ignorance, vacillation, and sinfulness, are stereotypically applied to women (Suchocki 58). Therefore, the idea of God is only a myth that defines men as superior beings and women as inferior.

Consequently, the author revolts against the injustice done to her through the following lines: “*Āmāharulē bōlnu bha'ēna. Hāmīlē du:Kha pāyaum̃ . Aba phērī hāmīlē nabōlēra bijñāna ra pravidhikō kākhamā janmi'ēkō chōrīharulā'ī ukusamukusamā pilsā'ēra hurkā'una hunna bhannē mērō niskarṣa hō.*” ‘The mothers did not speak. We got sad. It is my conclusion that we should not raise our daughters feel so exhaust in the lap of science and technology without talking.’ (Paudel; my trans; 193). It is depicted through these lines that the sufferings given to women by men are unbearable. The phrase “*Āmāharulē bōlnu bha'ēna. Hāmīlē du:Kha pāyaum̃*” ‘The mothers did not speak. We got sad’ highlights a concerning reality - the silence and exhaustion experienced by women in the face of societal expectations and gender discrimination. Thus, she seeks an alternative space where she would live her life of freedom by abolishing the patriarchal rule completely. The author says: Why is there a lack of willingness to talk about menstruation openly? Paudel points out that it is rooted in the society’s patriarchal system. “Menses is used as a means to body shame women, and this is deeply embedded in Nepali society to the point that we neither

reflect nor talk about it. Wherever possible we strike a conversation on taboos and myths.” She protests against those religious myths which gave men the freedom to rule over women. Thus, Paudel protests against patriarchy by protesting against religious myths through these autobiography.

2.3. Subversion of Patriarchy

The Subversion of Patriarchy in Radha Paudel’s “*Apabitra Ragat*” basically deals with the issue of gender that is responsible behind the suffering of the women particularly in the Nepalese male dominated society. Paudel shouts for dignified menstruation and subverts patriarchy by resisting male values of the society. In the society, women are only supposed to be limited on the domestic boundary created by the patriarchal society; they are supposed to be the toy of patriarchal hands. Apparently, women should be always submissive and they should not revolt against the norms and values created by the males of the society. A girl is taught to be a women and her feminine destiny is imposed on her by the society. The autobiography criticizes all the conventional boundaries made by the society that treat the women to be submissive in their whole life.

The concept of patriarchy which has been developed within feminist writings is not a single or simple concept but has whole variety of different meanings (Beechey 66). Patriarchy has presented women as a weaker sex in many literary works and paintings. Women are not aware that they have been objectified by men. Thus, men oppress women with the consensus of women themselves. Richard Johnson et al explain, “We can read many forms of black representation such as work of black

American women novelists as constructions and reconstructions . . . of complex identities under sustained historical pressure” (16). This point has been put further by Stephen J. Milner, “The text functioned as a palliative to male anxieties concerning the potentially disruptive effects of women within society” (583). The author try to dismantle such texts which men use as a defensive tool against women potential.

In the autobiography, subversion of patriarchy is visibly presented when the leading female character Radha breaks patriarchy system as the society defines or makes her to follow. Moreover, the research work deals with the issue of the subversion of patriarchy system by picturing the concept of new women. It challenges the previous gender roles and also predicts the upcoming changes that are going to happen in the society. Radha as the leading female character challenges the patriarchal norms and values and advocates on behalf of every other female. The constructed patriarchal society often portrays the women as weak, inferior and dependent but Radha being a nurse by profession denies following the patriarchy concept and revolt for her freedom.

The author rejects the patriarchal values through her revolutionary ideas. She advocates to end all taboos related to menstruation especially at the grass-root level and wants the new generations to know the reality of the cruel society. The author in the autobiography emphasizes: “*Uklanai nasaknē gari bhyāgutō banā'idi'ēkō huncha*” ‘It has made Unable to climb like a frog’ (Paudel; my trans; 188). She presents another facet. “Over a period of time, women have placed themselves and their physical wellbeing last on their list of priorities.” But the new generation is not going to stay quiet, they shall subvert the patriarchal values. Daly gives some examples of

this subversion. According to her, the usual meaning of “lust” is well known in the patriarchal society of excessive sexual desire. Thus, it is evil. But it is evil only because the patriarchal society portrays it to women. If the society is non-patriarchal, “lust” would have positive meanings such as “vigor”, “fertility”, “craving”, “eagerness”, and “enthusiasm” (60). Thus, the author wants to invent a discourse that is not phallogocentric. She wants everyone to learn that myths, fear and shame about menstruation take a deep toll on girls’ sense of dignity and self-worth and it should be eliminated.

Obviously, exploitation of women can be ended only when the women empower themselves, and challenge the oppressors. Daly contends that this exploitation is underpinned by “God as the paradigm for all patriarchs. . . [and] unless he is dethroned from . . . women’s consciousness, women will never be empowered as full persons” (58). In the same vein, the author challenges patriarchy as a whole in these extract, “*Sāṃskṛtika bandhanaharu nacuḍālikanai’balātkāra rōkchu’ bhannu hatkēlālē surya chēkchu bhannu jastai nai hō*” ‘Saying ‘I will stop rape’ without breaking the cultural bonds. It is like saying that you touch the sun with your palm’ (Paudel; my trans; 152)

She warns those males to shed off their disguise of religion or any institutions which they have cunningly constructed to control women. Thus, the author chooses to challenge men and their institutions to end their domination.

Patriarchy restricts women’s rights. But today’s women have started to speak for themselves. This is depicted in the following extract:

*Mērā āṁkhāharu usailā'ī khōjirahēkā thi'ē. Tara agāḍī, pachāḍī, dāyāṁ
bāṁyā ṭyāmilē chēlī'ēkō kunai pani puruṣa dēkhiṁna. Aṁha dēkhiṁna. Dēkhna
mana thiyō ēka puluka mātraī bha'ē pani. Hērna nahunē bālā'ī mēkha
marunajēla hērara kē kē vidhvansahuncha hērna mana thiyō.*

My eyes were looking for him. But in front, behind, right and left, I didn't see any men's who was covered by *ṭyāmilē*. She wanted to see her father *Mekh Marunjel*, I wanted to see what would be destroyed' (Paudel; my trans; 11)

In these lines, the author raised her voice against the patriarchy. She claims that women are not going to remain quiet and submissive. These new ways of thinking is the exact point of radical feminists who are “committed to getting at the root of male domination by understanding the source of power differentials . . . [tracing] back to male sexuality and the notion that heterosexual intercourse enacts male domination over women” (McAfee; par. 22).

The unequal distribution of masculinity and femininity to men and women respectively also generates the idea that men are superior to the women. The author has the self-respect for her and she also respects her traditional, religion and society. She wants to make dignified menstruation a priority.

*Bāpachi āmākō ṭikā lagā'idinē pālō āyō. Mailē āmālā'ī nahērī ṭikā thāpēm̃ ra
hātamā ḍhōgēm̃. Āmāpratikō biśvāsa, sam'māna, māyā ra mamatālē bhari'ēkō
mērō chāti katai napōkhiyōs bhannē cāhānā bhitrabhitrai dabā'ēra rākhēm̃ .
Āṁkhai'ākhāṁ manamanai vārtā garēra jhaṇḍai satraha varṣapachi āmā
chōrī milēra mahināvārīkō arkō baliyō sānlō tōḍyaum̃.*

After the father, it was time to put tika by mother. Without looking at mother, I put on the tika and I bow down in her hand, suppressed the desire inside that my chest full of trust, respect, love and affection for my mother should not go anywhere. After seventeen years of talking to each other, mother and daughter together broke another strong chain of menstruation. (Paudel; my trans; 58)

Moreover, she does not allow society including men to identify her as inferior. The author contradictory proposition is ironical; she is mocking the patriarchal values. This contradiction is in fact the reality because the values prevalent in a society are recognized as exclusively constructed to serve males 'interest. They disseminate these values in the name of, as Millet argues, "institutions such as the academy, the church, and the family, each of which justifies and reinforces women's subordination (35). In fact, contemporary "Education involves . . . reworking of prejudice (Johnson et al. 18). However, she says that those societies should have free and dignified menstruation as this move motivates many women to break the patriarchal system in the society. Therefore, to dismantle the old values, the author is ready to end the patriarchal values and aware society for dignified menstruation.

In the autobiography, Paudel voice appears in various manners with different narratives and subverts patriarchy. She widely discusses the various perspectives of women including social, economic, cultural as well as power discourses. It is showed that patriarchy always imposed power toward female and femininity always tries to create mutual understanding between each other. Due to the suppression women are compelled to revolt against patriarchy. In this regard, She says, "*Samaya anusāra vaijñānika byākhyā garaum̐ bhanēra kina bhandainan? Yastā dhērai kurā chan jahām̐*

puruṣaharu cukēkā chan” ‘Why don't they tell us to explain scientifically according to time? There are many things where men are wrong’ (Paudel ; my trans; 118).

Here, the speaker explains that the society has seen significant technological advancements but there is no transformation when it comes to patriarchy because it is deeply embedded in cultural and social norms that have developed over centuries. She states that eliminating patriarchy remains a persistent and ongoing struggle. She subverts patriarchy by breaking out the barrier made by male dominated society and practices.

The author not only subverts the patriarchy but also enhance women to fit in the contemporary world as bold citizen. In this regard she says:

Mailē uhāmlāṭ suninaṃ. Sunnē jamarkō pani garinaṃ. Pharkidā pani pharkina. Ēka sēkēṇḍa pani kurinaṃ .Kurnu jarurī pani ṭhāninaṃ. Kinabhanē mērō udēsya spaṣṭa thiyō didīharu jastai chimēkīkō bhaimśīgōṭhamā ga'ēra nabasnē mērō aḍāna thiyō.

I didn't listen to her. I didn't even try to listen. Even I didn't look turn back . I didn't wait even a second. I didn't think it was necessary to wait. Because my intention was clear, my decision was not to go to the neighbor's buffalo barn like my sisters. (Paudel; my trans; 25)

Above lines show that how a woman subverts patriarchy in the final stage. By making a bold decision females resist patriarchy and liberate from socio economic, political and cultural bond of the society. In short, the autobiography raises feminist voice though various narratives and events and persuade her characters to subvert

patriarchy. The author prioritizes that dignified menstruation is basic women's right.

Also, she motivates every woman to be brave and break the silence and shame of menstruation in the society to subvert the patriarchy.

CHAPTER 3

CONCLUSION

This thesis has analysed Radha Paudel's autobiographical novel *Apabitra Ragat [Unholy blood] dealing with "Subversion of Patriarchy"*. In this autobiography, the writer has portrayed the characters that have subverted the cruel patriarchal practices surrounding menstruation, discrediting and disintegrating taboos associated with it. The study focuses on the specific research questions: What patriarchal ideologies are depicted in the autobiography, why does the narrator subvert the patriarchal ideologies in the autobiography; and how does the narrator subvert the patriarchy in the autobiography. Likewise, the objective of this research is to identify patriarchal ideology and different kinds of menstrual taboos and stigmas practiced by orthodox Hindu religious people in Nepal. This research persuades the readers because it provides ample examples of how patriarchy can be subverted through rejection and revolution.

The first research question of this thesis is what patriarchal ideologies are depicted in the autobiography. The author has foregrounded the voice of Nepali women and her horrifying experiences who have recognized the dominance of patriarchy across multiple geographical areas of Nepal. The autobiography presents a picture of a world where social norms and religious constraints treat women as inferior beings. In the name of God and morality, women are ruled implicitly by men to the extent that male dominance is naturalized. Theology, as a patriarchal creation, plays a crucial role in marginalizing women. It teaches women to be submissive, quiet, tolerant, and loyal to men. Those women who possess these qualities are

considered ideal women or wives since male-centric religious scriptures are obeyed by women, their dominance has been engraved in their minds right from the time of early human civilization. The author is bold, activist, and strong enough to break patriarchal values in her autobiography. Nepali women adhere to traditional values and believe in a patriarchal society. However, Paudel intends to challenge society's patriarchal ideology. Likewise, *Apabitra Ragat* also portrays the social reality of the patriarchal society. She is an example for society to be followed by women.

Patriarchy values and system oppressed women that's why women have to protest these things. In her autobiography, she motivated to women become brave to subvert patriarchy.

Having been raised in a patriarchal society, through *Apabitra Ragat*, Paudel aims to show the irrelevancy of the patriarchal ideologies of the society. Hence, introducing a variety of female characters in her text, Paudel claims that females should have to subvert these patriarchal systems. Resting upon the themes of female solidarity, self-discovery, independence, adultery, and selflessness, Paudel's text aim to deconstruct the patriarchal ideologies and system behind women's representations as constructed by male. Paudel subverts the traditional roles that are assigned to women, which require that women grow up to be obedient, faithful, selfless, and subservient beings by defamiliarising. Subverting the dominant ideologies through the help of postmodern re-writing techniques, Paudel critique exposes the machinations that are at work in where patriarchal society. In a book talk session organized by Thames International College, Paudel stated "Until and unless we re-define the

lifestyles in far-west and mid-west Nepal, we cannot change the definition of Nepal.

The country can only prosper if rural areas are developed" (Paudel;par. 4).

The autobiography subverts patriarchy because it has marginalized women from social, religious to political sectors. It does so through apparently neutral institutions such as the academy, the church, and the family. These institutions justify and reinforce women's subordination to men, resulting in women internalizing a sense of inferiority to men. More significantly, it has defined peace in favor of men where peace means women remaining silent enduring male domination. If peace means maintaining silence, avoiding speaking, not giving any interpretation, and enduring attacks continuously, then it would be better for women to wage war. War is more beautiful than peace. She appeals to women to become bold and attain the pure joy of their will. Therefore, Paudel feels the need to subvert the patriarchy.

The autobiography depicts the world as patriarchal where women are treated as secondary beings. Though it seems neutral on a superficial level, there is hidden marginalization taking place within social and religious institutions. The author protests against this marginalization of women. The autobiography subverts patriarchal norms and values because they serve the interests of men, their norms and values are oppressive to women. The author also envisions a society in which everyone, regardless of gender, enjoys true happiness. This study has explored the subversion of patriarchy in *Apabitra Ragat*. Due to time constraints and limitations of this study, this thesis has left some issues like aesthetic aspects, regional novel, cultural studies and so on. Future researchers can do further study on these perspectives.

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